

ANYTHING NEW UNDER THE SUN? LOOKING BACK TO PIEPHO (1993) AND PUTZER (1991)

In commemoration of Babylonia's 30 years of valuable contributions, the following materials are intended to be used with pre-service teachers as prompts for discussions and ideas for creative teaching. The first stems from Piepho's 1993 work that encourages the use of learning styles in the classroom which nowadays we might look upon slightly more critically. The second, based on Putzer's 1991 article on assessment, shows how we teachers are still struggling to assess holistically and functionally in today's classrooms, so there nothing much has changed.

● **Laura Loder-Büchel** |
member of Babylonia's
editorial team

Over the years, there has been many an article written about learning styles and multiple intelligences. Including Piepho (1993). Yet through their over-mention at universities of teacher education, we might be propagating a “myth” - that students should study in a way that is appropriate to their learning style and that teachers should help learners identify their own learning styles and then teach individuals accordingly. But per-

haps, as newer research might attest, there is more that we all as learners have in common than what separates us and that as teachers, we may vary how we teach and encourage all learners to try out many different ways of studying without matching “learning styles” to “study styles”. Perhaps the categories are useful for teachers to think about for the aim of variation, but not so much for helping learners to study better.

Links

<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2018.00105/full>

<https://www.theguardian.com/education/2017/mar/12/no-evidence-to-back-idea-of-learning-styles>

<https://www.theatlantic.com/science/archive/2018/04/the-myth-of-learning-styles/557687/>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4658417/>

Piepho, H. (1993). Die Begegnung mit dem Anderen Überlegungen zur Kontinuität von der Primarschule zur Sekundarstufe. Babylonia. (2) pp. 70-75

LOLOBUE

FAKE NEWS!

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(Tip: You can click on any image that appears to change it.)

Name | Location | Date | Write today

Laura
earlier today....

OMG! Look what I read today!!
(Babylonia 2-1993, p. 72)
Kinder sind im 4. oder 5. Schuljahr genausowenig Kleinkinder, wie Kinder in der ersten Klasse der Sekundarstufe I junge Arbeiterinnen oder Arbeiter sind: es sind Heranwachsende mit Unterscheidungs- und Denkvermögen auf unterschiedlichen Niveaus der Abstraktion, der Anpassungsfähigkeit und des Behaltens, die sich schon deutlich in ihrem Lernertyp entwickelt haben.

- * expressive Lernertyp
- * autoritätsgebundene Regellerner
- * datensammelnde Lerner
- * musisch-rhythmische Lerner
- * Konzeptlerner

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Liked by you, Fakebook and 25 others

Marietta Papadatou-Pastou
earlier today....

No relationship was found between pupils' self-assessment and teachers' assessment, suggesting that teachers cannot assess the LS of their students accurately. Moreover, students' intelligence was not found to drive teachers' assessment of their LS. This study adds to the body of evidence that is skeptical of the adoption of LS in mainstream education.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2018.00105/full>

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The Guardian
earlier today....

"There are, however, a number of problems with the learning styles approach."
<https://www.theguardian.com/education/2017/mar/12/no-evidence-to-back-idea-of-learning-styles>

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Olga Khazan
earlier today....

"there's evidence that people do try to treat tasks in accordance with what they believe to be their learning style, but it doesn't help them," Daniel Willingham, a psychologist at the University of Virginia, told me. In 2015, he reviewed the literature on learning styles and concluded that "learning styles theories have not panned out."

<https://www.theatlantic.com/science/archive/2018/04/the-myth-of-learning-styles/557687/>

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Manuela Macedonia
earlier today....

However, despite the quantity of articles and practice books, websites on the topic, and investment in teacher training, there is no empirical evidence for the existence of learning styles.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4658417/>

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Tools

Class Tools

<https://www.classools.net/>

Class Tools offers myriad options for the classroom. Fakebook is brilliant for the example you see above where students read an article related to your course content. Then, they have to find something they could possibly disagree with or that they know has been disputed in the literature. This is what they post! I find this useful for critical thinking skills – often my students are not differentiated enough and are too willing to accept and not to question. Fakebook can also be used to try to walk in someone else’s shoes – to play the role of a character from a book or even an animal in the primary school!

Breaking News Generator

The other tool I tend to use here is the **Breaking News Generator**. This is fun to use as a provocation to get students talking or as a CAT (classroom assessment technique) at the end of the lesson where students post what they learned.

Using these tools often requires some peer correction – from language learning perspective, students have to produce language and have to find the right words. But they can be used for any topic, at any level.

In the first issue of *Babylonia* (0-1991), Oskar Putzer wrote about Testing and Assessment (Prüfen und Bewerten, p. 36) and his ideas are still relevant today. This page is intended for use in teacher training – as discussion prompts.

Putzer, O. (1991). Prüfen und Bewerten im Fremdsprachenunterricht. *Babylonia*, (1) pp. 36-37.

Fortune tellers, cootie catchers, whatever you want to call them are simple but add a little silliness to your teaching. Look online for ways to fold and adaptations and below is one related to assessment and testing that you can use with your students. The context should be whatever level you are teaching. For prompts that require spelling, each letter is a fold. For the prompts that require listing, for each item listed, there is one fortune teller fold.

